

The Contribution of women in the Indian National Army (1942-1945)

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Abstract: The Indian National Army founded in 1942 by Subhas Chandra Bose during second world war II .He was a prominent Indian Nationalist leader. Women played an important role in India at the time. Lakshmi Swaminathan, Janaki Thevar, and Saraswati Rajamani requires summarising their contribution to the Indian Independence movement, particularly their roles in the Rani of Jhansi Regiment. The bravery and commitment of the women in the Rani of Jhansi Regiment, though their combat action were limited but to the INA'S ultimate defeat, remain a powerful and inspiring chapter in India struggle Independence.

Keywords: Indian National Army, Rani of Jhansi, Dr. Laxmi swaminathan, Janaki Thevar, Saraswati Rajmani.

Introduction

The Indian National Army was a military force that split during world war II in Southeast Asia, including Singapore, Malaya and Burma. with the aim of liberating Indians from British Colonial rule. The INA was founded in 1942 by great Indian leader Subhas Chandra Bose. The contribution of women in the Indian National Army was a revolutionary step in Indian's freedom struggle In 1942. This led to the formation of the Rani Jhansi Regiment led by warrior women Dr. Lakshmi Swaminathan, was a prominent figure in the Indian Independence movement, a doctor and a social activist. Another warrior woman is Janaki Thevar, a 16 year old who gave up a life of luxury to battle for India's freedom in her country of origin. Saraswati Rajmani was an Indian freedom fighter and a veteran of the Indian National Army (INA), also known as Azad Hind Fouj. They proved that women were not just support of the cause but were capable, willing and brave soldiers in their own right.

Rani of Jhansi regiment:

The regiment was named after Rani Lakshmi Bai of Jhansi, a prominent figure in the Indian Rebellion of 1857. The Rani of Jhansi regiment was set up by Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose He announced the formation of the regiment on July 12, 1943 as part of his vision for the liberation of India.

Dr. Lakshmi Swaminathan

Lakshmi Swaminathan was born on Oct 24, 1914, in Madras (now

Chennai). She completed her MBBS degree from Madras Medical College in 1938 a diploma in gynecology and obstetrics in 1939. She worked as a doctor in the Government Kasturba Gandhi Hospital located at Triplicane Chennai. The Rani of Jhansi regiment was a unique and historically significant all-female combat regiment of the Indian National Army during world war II. It was a pioneer initiative that broke traditional gender barriers and symbolized the widespread desire for Indian Independence. The regiment was owned by Captain Lakshmi Swaminathan who later became famous as Captain Lakshmi Sahgal. She was a doctor who had been working in Singapore and deeply committed to the cause of Indian Independence. Captain Lakshmi was arrested by the British Army in May 1945, remaining in Burma until March 1946, when she was sent to India at a time when the INA trials in Delhi heightened popular discontent with and hastened the end of colonial rule. In 1971, Lakshmi Sahgal joined the communist party of India (Marxist) and represented the party in the Rajya Sabha. She was one of the founding members of All India Democratic Women's Association in 1981 and led many of its activities and campaigns. In 1998, Lakshmi Sahgal was awarded the Padma Vibhushan by Indian President K.R. Narayan. On 19 July 2012, Lakshmi Sahgal suffered a cardiac arrest and died on 23 July 2012 at the age of 97 at Kanpur. Her body was donated to Ganesh Shankar Vidyarthi Memorial Medical College for medical research.

Janaki Thevar

Janaki Thevar also known as Janaki Athi Nahapan, was a prominent figure in the Indian National Army, particularly in its all-female Rani of Jhansi Regiment. Her contributions were significant and multi-faceted. At a very young age, she joined the Rani of Jhansi Regiment, which was led by Netaji Subhas Chandra Bose. Her commitment and leadership were so notable that she became the commander of the regiment when she was just 18 years old. After the war, she continued her political and social work. She was one of the founding members of the Malaysian Indian Congress and later became a senator in the Malaysian Parliament. For her extraordinary service, she was honoured with the Padma Shri, she was the first woman of Indian origin living outside India to receive this award. Janaki Thevar is remembered as a courageous and dedicated leader who defied gender stereotypes and played an important role in the fight for freedom and welfare.

“We may be the softer and fairer sex but surely I protest against the word ‘weaker’. All sorts of epithets have been given to us by man to guard his own selfish interest. It is time we shattered these chains of men along with the chain of Indian slavery” —Janaki Thevar.

Saraswati Rajamani

Saraswati Rajamani was born in 1927 in Rangoon, Burma, Rajamani came from a very wealthy family with a strong history of supporting India's Independence Movement. Saraswati Rajamani was a remarkable Indian free-

dom fighter and one of the youngest spies of the Indian National Army. She was so inspired by Netaji Subhash Chandra Bose fiery speeches that she donated all of her gold and diamond jewellery to the INA to help fund the fight for freedom. Their journey began with chopping off their long hair and dressing up as boys to work as spies in the caps and houses of British officers. Joined the Rani of Jhansi Regiment and become India's first female spy adopting the alias "Mani" and disguising herself as a boy for two years to gather information of the British movement. Her work in the army ended when Netaji disbanded the INA after Britishers won World war II. The family unfortunately had to lead a life of penury on returning to India.

"As a boy, my name was mani. We diligently listened to all the conversation the British officers had, and later on, all five of us discussed the information we had collected and then conveyed it to Netaji. Those were very exciting days." said Rajmani in a 2005 interview with Shobha warrior. She also known as the "First Indian Female Spy."

Saraswati Rajamani passed away on January 13,2018,at the age of 91.She is remembered as an unsung hero and a true symbol of youthful bravery and dedication in the fight for India's Independence.

Conclusion

All three Women were driven by a strong sense of patriotism and were inspired by Netaji Subhas Chandra Bose's call for "total mobilization." Despite personal risk and the Hard ship of military life, they dedicated themselves to the INA mission. Lakshmi Sahgal, Janaki Thevar and Saraswati Rajamani are three remarkable women who played pivotal roles in the Indian National Army and its women's wing, the Rani of Jhansi regiment. While each had a unique role, their combined contribution form a powerful conclusion about the integral and multifaceted part women played in the armed struggle for India's Independence.

Lakshmi Sahgal: As a doctor and a revolutionary, she met with Bose and was given the mandate to form and lead the Rani of Jhansi Regiment. she was a commander of the Rani of Jhansi Regiment. leading the recruitment training and command of the all-female force. Her role was that of visionary leader, a direct counterpart to Subhas Chandra Bose, and only women in his cabinet. She also served as the minister of Women's Affairs in the Azad Hind Government.

Janaki Thevar: A young and dedicated soldier, Janaki Thevar role exemplified the courage and discipline of the rank to become the second-in-command of the regiment. Her contribution of testament to the effectiveness of the woman's army.

Saraswati Rajamani: Saraswati Rajamani role was different but equally vital As a teenager, she became one of the youngest spies in the INA military intelligence wing. Her contribution was rooted in stealth and deception, as she and her colleagues disguised themselves to gather crucial information on British troop movements and plans.

Their dedication, courage, and willingness to sacrifice everything for the nation fundamentally challenged conventional gender roles and proved that the fight for independence was a truly inclusive, national effort. Most of the volunteers were young, many in their teens, and had little to no prior military training. They underwent forbidding training

Military drills, route marches, and weapons training with rifles, bayonets and grenades some received advanced training in jungle warfare.

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